

**ASSESSING THE NURSERY PERFORMANCE OF CLONAL EUCALYPTUS
CUTTINGS THAT HAVE UNDERGONE DIFFERENT TIME DURATION
TREATMENTS BEFORE INSERTION.**

BY

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**A SPECIAL PROJECT REPORT SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF FORESTRY,
ENVIRONMENTAL AND GEOGRAPHICAL SCIENCES IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR A BACHELOR OF SCIENCE
DEGREE IN FORESTRY OF MAKERERE UNIVERSITY.**

NOVEMBER, 2022.

DECLARATION:

I, Akantambira Owen declare that this research work is my original work, a result of my own efforts, and has never been submitted to any institution for any award or assessment.

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APPROVAL:

This work has been compiled and submitted to the School of Forestry, Environmental and Geographical Sciences, with the approval of my supervisor;

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DEDICATION:

I unreservedly dedicate this work to my gracious Lord God Jesus Christ, for the due providence; as well as to my cherished family for all the social and financial support, during my whole course of study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

My utmost gratitude is unto the Most High and true God, Jesus Christ who granted me all it took for me to come up with this research in form of providence and provision of all sorts; blessed be His mighty loving name.

I must also acknowledge the academic staff at the School of Forestry, Environmental and Geographical Sciences for the forestry-related knowledge and skills I have acquired from them which was crucial in coming up with this research.

In particular, I specially wish to express gratitude to my supervisor, Assoc. Prof Fred Babweteera, who tirelessly offered to provide the guidance and knowledge to me, amidst his busy schedules, without which I wouldn't have been able to come up with such work.

I also wish to convey my sincere thanks to the administration of the National Tree Seed Center for giving me the opportunity to conduct my study from their place, as well as allowing me to use their tools/facilities during my study.

My family's financial and social support can't be left unrecognised, and on this note I extend my heartfelt credit to my lovely cherished parents for all the parental care and support rendered, as well as to all my siblings.

Lastly, sincere appreciation goes to any academic colleagues of mine that have rendered any kind of assistance to me during my course of study.

MAY THE FAITHFUL GOD JESUS CHRIST REWARD YOU ALL, ACCORDING TO THE MEASURE OF HIS RICHES!!!

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LIST OF ACRONYMS:

GC	Grandis x Camaldulensis
GU	Grandis x Urophylla
CFRs	Central Forest Reserves
NTSC	National Tree Seed Centre
UWA	Uganda Wildlife Authority
NFA	National Forestry Authority
SPGS	Sawlog Production Grant Scheme
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
SPSS	Social Package for Social Scientists
NaFFORI	National Forest Resources Research Institute

ABSTRACT:

Hybrid clonal technology can radically change the way in which Eucalyptus plants are selected and grown. It offers a means of producing planting materials with highly desirable growth characteristics. Propagation by cuttings is the main tool in Eucalyptus breeding programs by which it is possible to multiply the Eucalyptus trees quickly as well as retaining the parental plant characteristics. This doesn't occur under natural conditions, it is therefore affected by different factors such as rooting media, nature and management of cuttings, which should be manipulated appropriately to get increased nursery output. This study was conducted at NTSC, to determine the best time duration within which cutting insertion should be done. Three eucalyptus hybrids were considered i.e. GC796, GC796/2 and GU7. 150 cuttings were used for each clonal type, with 50 cuttings for each of a 60-minute difference time treatment. 50-cutting batches for each of the three clones were inserted at 60, 120, and 180 minutes respectively after harvesting.

GC796 and GC796/2 clones attained the highest survival percentage for cuttings inserted at 120 minutes, whereas GU7 had the highest survival percentage with cuttings inserted at 60 minutes. GU7 exhibited a consistent reduction in survival percentage with increasing time of insertion while GC796 had the lowest survival percentage for cuttings inserted at 60 minutes as GC796/2 attained the lowest survival percentage with cuttings inserted at 180 minutes, which was the same case with GU7. GC796/2 registered the highest survival percentages whereas GU7 exhibited the lowest survival percentage under all treatments. Only GC796 cuttings registered a significant difference, in the number of roots between 60 and 180 minutes, and in the length of the longest root between 60 and 120 minutes. Given that GU7 cuttings were more sensitive to the effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion, it is recommended that its cuttings be inserted immediately after cutting preparation. The study further recommends that more studies should be done under strict control of all other influencing factors as well as using a larger sample size since this study was associated with a smaller sample size due to cutting mortality, i.e. cutting survival was generally poor.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Forest ecosystems are a critical component of the world's biodiversity as many forests are more bio-diverse than other ecosystems. According to the report by FAO, forests cover 31 percent of the global land area, whereby approximately half of the forest area is relatively intact, and more than a third is primary forest: the total forest area being 4.06 billion hectares, or approximately 5000 square metres (FAO & UNEP, 2020)

Since 1990, it is estimated that 420 million hectares of forest have been lost through conversion to other land uses: deforestation and forest degradation continue to take place at alarming rates, which contribute significantly to the ongoing loss of biodiversity, although the rate of deforestation has decreased over the past three decades. (FAO & UNEP, 2020), yet over 90 percent of the people living in extreme poverty, are dependent on forests for at least part of their livelihoods. This therefore, together with the increased global demand for wood, intensifies the need for plantation forestry as the only way to address the wood scarcity problem and also to help suppress the demand for illegally logged timber from natural forests which is a major issue globally (Gabriel, Marcos, & Teotonio, 2014)

About 4 % of the world's forests are plantations, established to provide a variety of ecosystem services as well as other direct and indirect benefits to biodiversity through the provision of forest habitat for a wide range of species, and by reducing negative impacts of natural forests by offsetting need to extract resources. (Stephen et al, 2013). Furthermore, given the trending concern of climate change globally, the potential of unmanaged natural forests to adapt to climate change impacts is somewhat limited unlike the plantation forests whose adaptive potential is far greater, as forest managers can alter silvicultural regimes and tree species composition to maintain the productive and thus economic capacity of these forests to adapt to or mitigate the effects of climate change .

The genus *Eucalyptus* is the most widely cultivated forest tree in the world owing principally to its diverse genome, its site-adaptability, and relatively fast growth rates and it comprises more than 900 species with various hybrids and varieties (Oballa et al, 2010). Approximately half of all plantation forestry in the tropics and subtropics is composed of *Eucalyptus* species (SPGS, 2011). Europeans introduced eucalyptus to eastern Africa during the second half of the 19th century and later at the beginning of the 20th century. The introduction of eucalyptus in

these countries seems to have followed serious forest decline and the emergence of wood deficit in these countries.

Uganda's forest resources are an essential foundation for the country's current and future livelihood and growth (NDP III). Over 90% of Uganda's energy requirement, for example, is generated by forests. The total forested area of the country is about 3.6 million ha, which is 15% of the total land area and 36% of the forests are owned by government, and the rest (64%) is under private ownership (John, 2011). Of the 3.6 million ha, 17% consist of CFRs managed by the NFA, 18% consists of national parks and wild reserves of which 0.85% is jointly managed by NFA and UWA, and 0.03% are local forest reserves managed by respective local governments. The rest of the forests, 64%, are on private and communal lands, and hence managed by private and local community forest owners.

According to NFA (John, 2011), by the end of 2010, the country had 62,230 ha of plantation forests; public and private sectors owned 14 140 ha (23%) and 48 090 ha (77%) respectively. Currently forest plantations only cover 0.2% of all forestland in the country or about 34,000 hectares. About 65% of this is government owned while the rest, is privately or customarily owned (FAO, 2020). It was therefore recommended that the government of Uganda should put in place a regulatory framework, which will create a positive investment climate to encourage private sector investment in commercial forest plantations.

Furthermore with the increasing pressures on the forest resources which are evident through the forest cover loss in Uganda that has increased to an estimated 200,000 hectares annually, as indicated by studies conducted by African Natural Resources Institute (Josephat, 2018). Consequently, the forest sector carried out several policies, legal and institutional reforms aimed at promoting the conservation and sustainable use of the country's forest resources; among which include, National Forestry Policy 2001, enactment of the National Forestry and Tree Planting Act 2003 which grants a license to interested responsible bodies and persons for the sustainable utilization and management of the forests, etc. (Musasizi, 2017) which has encouraged an augmented tree growing by the private growers, that have employed some improved tree planting techniques like vegetative propagation.

According to the report by National Forestry Authority (John, 2018), 182 licenses were issued for various activities in the Central Forest Reserves, which include harvesting on private plantations in CFRs as well as tree planting and research activities in the CFRs.

In Africa, Eucalyptus is the most widely planted genus covering 22.4% of all planted area, (Chamshama & Nwonwu, 2004). Eucalyptus was introduced to Uganda around 1912 to supply fuel wood for railways and administrative centers as well as to drain swamps in an attempt to prevent malaria. (Gessesse & Taklu, 2009). Nevertheless, supply of sufficient good quality seed is a major constraint in establishing and developing improved eucalyptus forest plantations. This challenge can be effectively counteracted by using a strategy of clonal forestry whereby the plantation trees are produced from cuttings harvested from a limited supply of stock plants derived from seedlings (Amanda, David, Matthew, Stephen, Adkins, & Helen, 2012)

Hybrid clonal technology can radically change the way in which Eucalyptus plants are selected and grown, and it offers a means of producing planting materials with highly desirable growth characteristics that result in superior wood products with high calorific value (KilimoTrust, 2011). Vegetative propagation technique is the handiest way to multiply Eucalyptus in industrial forestry as well as in forest research institutes (Palanisamy & Selvaraj., 2015). Eucalyptus hybrids are mainly grown for domestic and industrial fuel wood (John, 2011) and have shown promise in trials that could become important in the future

Hybrid clones of (GC) and (GU) were imported from South Africa in 2002/2003, and trial plots of provenances were established in different parts of the country (N.E. et al., 2016). The clones have shown tremendous, potential to expand the plantable area for eucalypts in Uganda, even in drier and hotter sites (John, 2011). Clonal eucalyptus is important to Uganda's economy, environment and people's livelihoods. This is due to its high carbon sequestration potential and ability to produce high volumes of utilizable products in a short time (Yonah & Christine, 2015)

1.2 Problem statement

Numerous pure tree species, and yet more tree hybrid clones have been globally deployed in plantations, as the forestry industry seeks to meet growing demands for wood and their products. As a result, various propagation approaches have been explored, from seeds to in vivo and in vitro propagation, with a view to remaining cost-effective, yet efficient, and sustainable (Shri & Muhammad, 2016). The in vivo and in vitro propagation of Eucalypts is preferred, as it conserves valuable germplasm and offers predictability in commercial forest plantations. However, most farmers have little knowledge on the appropriate procedure for successful clonal technology, where performance of the cuttings in the nursery and in the field

is still stumpy. This is mostly due to the influence of conditions that result into loss of rooting success some of which may be genetic, nutritional, environmental and/or genetic and environmental interaction, which at times may be as low as 20.0% (Sciences, n.d.). Loss of rooting success may be due to such factors as fungal infections, time lapse before cutting insertion, poor quality or quantity of rooting hormone, unfavourable temperature / humidity, etc (Rambaran, 2013). The factor of time lapse before cutting insertion has however not been particularly studied to determine the magnitude of its effect on rooting success.

1.3 Objectives of the study:

1.3.1 General objective

To assess the effect of time taken before cutting insertion into the pots on the nursery performance of Eucalyptus hybrid cuttings, in order to improve on the tree nursery performance of clonal trees that in turn will lead to increased tree nursery output.

1.3.2 Specific objectives

1. To assess the effect of time lapse taken between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on the survival of selected eucalyptus hybrid cuttings.
2. To ascertain the effect of time taken before cutting insertion into the pots on the root development of selected eucalyptus hybrid cuttings
3. To determine the effect of time between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion into the pots on the subsequent leaf development of selected eucalyptus hybrid cuttings

1.4 Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant difference in the survival of cuttings inserted after different time intervals

H₀: There is no significant difference in the root development of cuttings inserted after different time intervals

H₀: There is no significant difference in the leaf development of cuttings inserted after different time intervals

1.5 Significance of the study

This research aimed at determining the best time lapse between the coppice harvesting and cutting insertion, so as to add on the existing body of knowledge on the production of improved hybrid Eucalyptus. Ascertaining the best time at which eucalyptus clonal cuttings should be inserted into the pots contributes to better nursery performance which positively affects the field performance in turn. This will reduce economic losses as a result of poor nursery performance by enhancing increased nursery output of eucalyptus hybrid plantlets, which in turn will lead to an improved eucalyptus clonal forestry, as well as increased profit realisation by the farmers.

1.6 Scope

The experiment involved three eucalyptus hybrid species, i.e. GC796, GC796/2 and GU7, all of which were subjected to the same experimental design. Four hundred fifty cuttings, were subcategorised according to tree species and time interval factor giving rise to nine samples of three clonal eucalyptus specie groups, with each group being subjected to three different durations before cutting insertion.

The first three lots sub-grouped by species, of fifty, were processed and inserted within one hour and the other six lots within two and three hours respectively, three lots per each hour.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Eucalyptus growing

Eucalypts are extensively planted on a massive scale worldwide for fuelwood, poles, timber and other wood products (Spgs, 2009). They are however endemic to Australia and the neighbouring northern islands, and are important because of their being adaptive, productive, fast-growing, resistant (Winarni et al., 2021) among others. Currently, Eucalyptus has spread to most regions of the world (IUFRO, 2018), and they are one of the most commonly grown tree species in tropical timber plantations (Dwi Sulichantini et al., 2014) covering more than 19 million hectares, and, dominating the global plantation forestry industry (Wamalwa & Oeba, 2005). Their adoption has led to a decrease in indigenous timber tree species, (N.E. et al., 2016) which case together with the need for timber and other wood products, increased the need for faster growing species to meet the increasing demands .

Eucalypts are the most widely planted hardwood species in the world (Ramlal, 2014), and their optimal growth is favoured on acidic soil, in the presence of adequate moisture and suitable temperatures. It is noted that eucalyptus prefers sandy loam soil with an alkaline pH not less than 8 (Winarni et al., 2021).

There is a great deal of eucalyptus species that have been planted throughout the tropics and sub-tropics though nine species have been the most used i.e. *E. camaldulensis*, *E. globulus*, *E. grandis*, *E. maculata*, *E. paniculata*, *E. robusta*, *E. saligna*, *E. urophylla*, and *E. viminalis* (Health & Papers, 2004) with over 100 species of this genus grown in East Africa. The success and widespread cultivation of eucalyptus species is because of their fast growth rate, short rotation time and high adaptability to a wide range of environments (Rambaran, 2013) and the ease with which it can be cultivated and managed, which make them desirable species for both large and small scale forestry. Unlike eucalypts, most other tree genera may not possess the ability to thrive on marginal sites (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016).

Eucalyptus is a commercially important genus that provides varied uses in the timber, pulp and pharmaceutical industries (Louppe, 2010), in addition to the provision of firewood, charcoal, and essential oils (Spgs, 2009).

2.2 Eucalyptus growing in Uganda

In Uganda, *E. grandis* is the most predominant species (Trust, 2011), however, there have been tree improvement initiatives over the years (Mankessi et al., 2010), focusing on the use of

Eucalyptus hybrid clones by the virtue of their genetic superiority, with important traits such as pest and disease resistance, fast and uniform growth (Nakabonge & Matovu, 2021) as well as homogenous physical properties.

2.3 Eucalyptus hybrid clones

Generally, clones are genetically identical plants which are not reproduced from seed but by specialized means such as rooted cuttings or tissue culture (Trust, 2011), with the rooted cuttings being the predominantly used in Eucalyptus clonal propagation, since tissue culture requires more advanced technology.

Eucalyptus trees raised through this method are called clones because they are duplicated genetic copies of the original individuals (Oballa et al., 2010). Eucalyptus species that are raised through vegetative methods include; *Eucalyptus grandis*, *Eucalyptus saligna*, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Eucalyptus urophylla*, as well as their hybrids. Hybrids can only be raised through vegetative methods, widely known as cloning (Brondani, de Wit Ondas, et al., 2012)

Eucalyptus hybrids are crosses between two different eucalyptus species, with the most popular ones being hybrids of GCs (Oballa et al., 2010). Hybrids of these two species combine the fast growth of *Eucalyptus grandis* and the drought tolerance of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*.

Eucalyptus hybrid clones combine the desirable properties from different eucalypts such as fast and uniform growth, high productivity, small crowns, resistance to pests and diseases, and straight stems which lead to a good quality, highly marketable product (Trust, 2011) and are produced through natural tree breeding programmes.

Eucalyptus hybrid cloning is not genetic modification i.e. the direct human manipulation of genetic material in such a way that artificial technologies are employed; thereby not occurring under natural conditions (Trust, 2011)

2.4 Eucalyptus hybrid clone growing in Uganda

Mass vegetative propagation has become an important tool for increasing the competitiveness of the forestry based industry (Selvan, 2015) and it is considered as one of the main methods to produce good eucalypt plantlets (Dwi Sulichantini et al., 2014). Clonal propagation is one of the best strategies for designing the improvement program of eucalyptus species (Winarni et al., 2021). This method reaches its highest potential when it is used to establish clonal forests of hybrids endowed with better wood quality and higher volumetric growth (Titon et al., 2006).

Clonal eucalyptus hybrids have proved to possess desirable traits of faster growth and adaptability to different climatic conditions (Oballa et al., 2010). Eucalypt clones were introduced from Mondi South Africa to Uganda during the period of 1997 to 2003 (N.E. et al., 2016). This was as well triggered by a huge supply gap due to increased demand for wood and its products from the high population growth and growing construction industry in Uganda (Ministry of Water and Environment, 2016). This supply gap prompted the Saw log production and grants scheme (SPGS, 2013) National Forestry Authority, Forest Sector support division and Civil Society in Uganda to promote growth of clones.

Clonal eucalypts were introduced in Uganda in 2002 by NaFORRI from Mondi owned forest plantations in South Africa under the Tree Biotechnology Project-Uganda (Ngamau et al., 2004) with an aim of introducing, testing and demonstrating clonal forestry and producing suitable clones. 13 trials were made in the main agro-ecological zones of Uganda in 2002 and 2003 on 12 clonal eucalypts including 5 hybrids of GUs, 6 hybrids of GCs and one pure *Eucalyptus grandis* hybrid (Ngamau et al., 2004).

The silvicultural assessment results from NaFFORI were good with some of the clones showing very good growth rates, as a result over 800,000 plantlets were released to commercial tree growers by the end of 2009 (Tree et al., 2009).

The objective of hybrid *Eucalyptus* introduction in Uganda was to improve the standards of living of the rural communities, particularly the resource poor group among the rural population (Turinawe et al., 2014), which was to be achieved particularly through bringing about sustainable production of the forest resources such as poles, timber, firewood, etc. This was so because of population increase where by the natural sources of fuel wood could no longer keep pace with the associated demand, which had resulted in the onset of deforestation thereby leading to the degrading of the environment (Selvan, 2015)

Not only was it an issue of population increase but also a serious problem of pest infestation in the existing *Eucalyptus* species by then, such as *Leptocybe invasa* (Nyeko et al., 2009), *Botryosphaeria* canker disease (Jimu et al., 2016) etc. The emergence of these problems prompted the idea to opt for the appropriate option to counteract the situation, which was to grow hybrid *Eucalyptus* with clonal technology (Kirongo et al., 2014).

2.5 Propagation of Eucalypts.

Whereas most species of *Eucalyptus* can be propagated by both seeds and vegetative propagation, i.e. either by cuttings or by grafting (Bryant & Trueman, 2015), *Eucalyptus* hybrid

clones can only be effectively propagated by vegetative means. This is more preferable in tree propagation especially where use of seeds is faced with many challenges or where use of seeds is exclusively impossible. On the account of this, efforts for propagation by cutting of hybrid Eucalyptus were put in place (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016), as a strategy for addressing these drawbacks (Saya et al., 2008).

2.5.1 Sexual propagation of Eucalyptus

Naturally, Eucalyptus breeding happens from seeds which are collected and used to establish commercial plantations (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016), wood lots, tree orchards, etc. This is the oldest, easiest and most conventional method of propagation of Eucalyptus (Titon et al., 2006) which is still being used mostly by local small scale farmers, where by most resultant plantations of seed propagation are characterized by variations in characteristics such as growth rate, form and vigor, etc. (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016) which is as a result of a varied diversity of genes inherited from differing mother trees (Wightman, n.d.), unlike for clonal hybrids, which exhibit a high level of uniformity in most of the growth parameters (Ngamau et al., 2004).

With the rapid technological development of biotechnology in the past years, many unconventional techniques have been developed to raise or propagate elite trees without using seeds as the source of the germplasm (Kirongo et al., 2014). Notwithstanding, natural eucalypt forests and planted eucalypt stands remain the initial sources of eucalypt material for commercial activities and breeding programmes with wide genetic bases and thus are central to the conservation of genetic diversity within the Eucalyptus genus (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016)

2.5.2 Asexual propagation of Eucalyptus

Asexual/vegetative propagation of the genus Eucalyptus is carried out to a greater extent in most of the forestry companies that have adopted clonal forestry to continuously raise Eucalyptus hybrids, since it is considered strategic for improving forest yield and quality (Titon et al., 2006). Due to lack of seed genetic viability, most hybrid genotypes experience difficulty in producing sufficient quantities of seed because of irregular flowering and high abortion (Rambaran, 2013). Even when some seeds are produced, they often experience very low germination capabilities (Glocke et al., 2006) which calls for new approaches to continuously improve the efficiency of Eucalyptus propagation schemes since there is increasing demand for planting material (Rambaran, 2013). To meet this demand of the planting stock, eucalyptus plants are being produced by means of vegetative propagation since this technique is the handiest way to multiplying Eucalyptus in commercial forestry as well as in forest research institutes (Selvan, 2015).

By the virtue of the fact that some species of Eucalyptus have the ability to hybridize naturally (Rambaran, 2013), hybridization has therefore become a very important practice in tree improvement programmes (Griffin, 2014) since the combination of desirable genetic traits from the two different species results in superior eucalypt genotypes capable to grow on marginal sites (Rambaran, 2013) which has contributed to a gradual shift from sexual to asexual eucalyptus propagation.

In commercial forestry, the purpose of asexual propagation is to consolidate the genetic gain and to mass multiply superior trees like Eucalyptus (Selvan, 2015), thereby producing individual trees that are identical to each other and to the parent plant (Trust, 2011). The commercial cloning of Eucalyptus began in 1975 in the Republic of Congo and it is important for maintenance of genetic characteristics of desirable parent trees (Brondani, Wendling, et al., 2012). Some of the methods practised with vegetative propagation include grafting, budding, layering and cuttings where by use of cuttings is particularly the most vegetative method used for Eucalyptus propagation. (Selvan, 2015).

2.5.2.1 Propagation of Eucalyptus clones by cuttings

There are various methods of propagation through cuttings used with eucalyptus hybrids, that have been documented, some of which include; leafy cuttings, cladode cuttings; stem/branch cuttings (Selvan, 2015) etc. In eucalyptus, stem/branch cuttings are the predominantly used worldwide in clonal Eucalyptus propagation for commercial plantings (Selvan, 2015).

Vegetative propagation by cuttings is the main tool in Eucalyptus breeding programs by which it is possible to multiply the Eucalyptus trees quickly as well as retaining the parental plant characteristics (Selvan, 2015).

With vegetative propagation, superior eucalypt genotypes can be identified from natural populations and then screened for the desired character traits, and then propagated on a large scale (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016).

Eucalyptus trees displaying the desirable character traits are identified , felled and the coppice used as rooted cuttings (Murugan, 2007). However, this method is associated with wastage of land and therefore introduction of clonal hedges was found more suitable (D. Naidu & Jones, 2016). The eucalypt clonal hedge gardens are areas planted with Eucalyptus trees which are later clipped at a height of about 25-30cm (Mankessi et al., 2010) and then used as ortets from which sprouts can continuously be harvested and used for raising new clonal eucalyptus

plantlets (D. Naidu & Jones, 2016). These ortets serve the purpose of parent plants by providing a constant source of cutting (Titon et al., 2006).

Notwithstanding, propagation by cuttings is limited to a small number of Eucalyptus species and hybrids (Brondani, de Wit Ondas, et al., 2012) which is mainly due to the fact that cuttings from different species display varied rooting abilities (Trueman, et al., 2018), some which display substantive lower abilities.

2.6 Management of the clonal Eucalyptus mother garden

In order to ensure higher rooting capabilities in Eucalyptus clones, parent ortets need to be maintained in the juvenile phase as this makes it easy for the undifferentiated cells to produce all plant tissues (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004).

Given the fact that conventional clonal hedge system enables the mass production of propagules, being outdoors means they are highly affected by the weather (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016) and since it is difficult to control weather, management of these clonal hedges requires intensive skilled labor (Brondani, de Wit Ondas, et al., 2012).

There are varied factors that affect the success of Eucalyptus clonal propagation when it comes to the rooting success of cuttings, and the loss of juvenility in parent plants is one of them that can cause a serious reduction in rooting ability of the cuttings (Trueman, et al., 2018), however much it is not the only important factor that affects rooting of cuttings. There are many other factors responsible for variation in rooting ability of cuttings including the type of media used (Jeremiah et al., 2018), length of cuttings (Saya et al., 2008), topophysis (Rambaran, 2013), among others.

Plant nutrition of the parent plants is another key factor affecting the ability of the cuttings to give rise to plantlets in any given media mixtures (Murugan, 2007), since it influences the amount of carbohydrates, auxins and metabolic compounds, all of which are necessary for effective rooting of cuttings (Brondani, de Wit Ondas, et al., 2012). Therefore, parent plants should be well supplied with macronutrients like phosphorus, potassium and nitrogen, as well as micro nutrients such as calcium and magnesium that should be moderate (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004).

Also, light and temperature conditions to which the parent plants are exposed can influence the rooting in the harvested cuttings. It is however possible to manipulate these conditions to ensure maximum rooting of cuttings (Mokotedi et al., 2000), and therefore they should be maintained at optimal levels. These factors can influence the uptake and metabolism of nutrients and

hormones, (Selvan, 2015). Light, specifically affects the levels of carbohydrate in parent plants which should be sufficient not only to supply the cuttings with the energy required to initiate roots, but also to regulate rooting (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004). The temperature to which parent plants are subjected have the potential to affect the quality and quantity of cuttings produced, (Rambaran, 2013) as well as the associated root development.

2.7 Factors affecting Eucalyptus cloning

27.1 Length of the cuttings

Cutting length was established as one of the key factors associated with rooting ability, whereby increased cutting length was found to be positively associated with rooting (Dick et al., 2004). Cutting length can affect rooting of clonal cuttings as it is an important causal factor of within and between-shoot variation in rooting ability (Dick et al., 2004; R. D. Naidu & Jones, 2009). Determining optimal cutting length is therefore essential as a very long cutting would be a waste of valuable coppice material, with limited or no benefit in rooting percentage, (Saya et al., 2008) whereas a short cutting may not result in the development of sufficient roots possibly due to a lack of sufficient storage reserves (Richard, 2022). Nevertheless, it established that, longer, thicker cuttings display higher initial growth but the differences tend to disappear over time.

Furthermore, the study by (R. D. Naidu & Jones, 2009) found that there was a significant cutting length effect on rooting percentage whereby the smallest cuttings (5cm long) had the lowest rooting as the longer cuttings (8cm) displayed higher rooting percentages; which nonetheless after decreased with further increases in cutting length.

It is thus recommended that the overall average cutting length should be approximately 8–10 cm (R. D. Naidu & Jones, 2009; Winarni et al., 2021) for Eucalyptus hybrid clones from conventional hedges, with a 5 to 8 cm long basal internode (Saya et al., 2008) for optimal production.

2.7.2 Nutritional factors

Plant nutrition of the parent plants is a key factor that affect the ability of the cuttings to develop into new plantlets (Murugan, 2007), since it influences the amount of carbohydrates, auxins and metabolic compounds, all of which are necessary for effective rooting of cuttings (Brondani, de Wit Ondas, et al., 2012). Therefore, parent plants should be well supplied with macronutrients like phosphorus, potassium and nitrogen, as well as micro nutrients such as calcium and magnesium that should be moderate (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004). An

increased nitrogen concentration promotes greater photosynthetic activity which encourages biomass production (Rambaran, 2013). On the other hand, endogenous nitrogen content is negatively correlated with the rooting of *Eucalyptus urophylla* cuttings though positively, with that of *Eucalyptus grandis* cuttings (Titon et al., 2006).

2.7.3 Topophysis

Topophysis is referred to as the effect of the position of the propagule on the plant upon the type of vegetative growth subsequently shown by the vegetative progeny. Cuttings taken sequentially down a stem have variable rooting abilities due to chronological, morphological and physiological differences at different positions of the stem (Rambaran, 2013).

Usually, eucalyptus rametes are composed of stems and branches, so during harvesting, only stems must be harvested as they would give rise to a sturdy straight plantlets (trees) as opposed to branches. This is due to the difference in their water, carbohydrate, nutrient and hormone concentrations. The branches are characterized by their being at an angle away from the vertical axis on the ramete whereas the stems appear to be in a vertical orientation.

It was noted that (Hansen, 1989) the cutting position on the stock plant has only a minor effect on the speed of root formation, but with a pronounced effect on the speed of axillary bud break. The best rooting of cuttings is usually found in cuttings from the more basal portions of a shoot (Hansen, 1989). It is also however argued that since auxin is synthesized in regions of active growth and young leaves, apical cuttings may contain more endogenous auxin available for root induction, thereby enabling apical cuttings to survive and root better than axillary cuttings (Blythe et al., 2007; Rambaran, 2013)

Cutting position may influence root development as a result of changes in the degree of juvenility along the stem or by gradual changes in environmental conditions such as irradiance and light quality which may vary along the stem in a population of vertically growing stock plants (Hansen, 1989). A study by Borges et al., (2011) (Rambaran, 2013) showed that apical *E. grandis* x *E. globulus* cuttings were superior to non-apical cuttings with regards to survival (80% compared with 40%) and rooting (90% compared with 65%) abilities.

2.7.4 Diameter of the cuttings

To develop clones, appropriate diameter of cuttings is very essential for increased rooting percentage; thinner and thicker cuttings will root, (Rana & Sood, 2012) but the number of roots initiated per cutting or the percentage of rooted cuttings is normally low for thinner cuttings. According to (Rambaran, 2013), the optimum diameter for hybrid eucalyptus cuttings is 3 mm,

however, the basal diameter range should vary between 2 – 5 mm (Stape et al., 2001) The diameter below 2 mm could indicate that the cuttings are still too young whereas beyond 5 mm, they are too mature and if used would result into low rooting percentage (Stuepp et al., 2017). It was also noted that hard woody cuttings show a greater rooting percentage than soft wood cuttings (Dhiman & Gandhi, 2014a) and this is attributed to thicker cuttings having greater carbohydrate reserves, which are required to promote rooting (Jr, 2003). However, a study by (Profile, 2015) indicated that as the diameter size of cuttings increase, both their survival and rooting decrease.

According to the study by (Figueiredo et al., 2011), it was established that there is partial correlation between the stem diameter of the cutting and height of the three month-trees after planting.

2.7.5 Rooting hormone application

Several studies have indicated that the success of vegetative propagation via cuttings is determined by adventitious root induction and development (Sevik & Guney, 2013) which can be enhanced by applying the commercial rooting hormones such as Rootex and Seradix, (Nor Aini et al., 2010) indole-3-butyric acid in clonal tree nurseries. It is well established that auxins are a key determinant in the process of adventitious root formation (Rambaran, 2013). In addition, auxins are responsible for a wide array of developmental responses and processes (Maraschin & Fett-neto, 2013) such as embryo patterning, vascular differentiation, root and shoot patterning and tropisms (Phuyal et al., 2018).

Due to the recalcitrance of adventitious root formation in many tree species, the application of exogenous hormones becomes a major approach for optimizing clonal propagation (Zhao et al., 2022). Therefore, the application of appropriate exogenous hormones has a significant effect on the rooting of cuttings of different species (Zhao et al., 2022) since endogenous auxins may not suffice the hormonal growth needs of the cuttings. . It was noted that increasing the nutrient supply to stock plants increases growth rate and rate of adventitious root production of subsequently harvested cuttings (Dick et al., 2004) . The concentrations at which these hormones are applied are proportional to their respective stabilities in plant tissues (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016), i.e. the least stable auxins, IAA, is used at a higher concentration of about 1 to 50 mg l⁻¹, whereas the more stable auxins are generally used at lower concentrations of about 10 mg l⁻¹.

These commercial rooting hormones can be made from indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) which is generally the most abundant endogenous auxin in plants, (Sevik & Guney, 2013) indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) and naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) which are effective in promoting rooting (Khajehpour et al., 2014). It is established that IBA and NAA are relatively more effective than IBA, which may be attributed to greater stability, longer persistence in tissues, as well as differences in metabolism and transport (Liu et al., 2022). Most clonal eucalyptus nurseries producing plantlets now find it inevitable to use rooting hormone, i.e. exogenous auxins since it is an efficient way of improving rooting percentages; speed, quality and uniformity of the roots produced; as well as the plantlets that emerge (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004). According to (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004; Rambaran, 2013), the type, concentration, form and time of auxin application varies with the species involved, the type of cutting selected and their age.

A study by (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004) showed that, with *E. grandis* x *E. urophylla* cuttings, the application of IBA was more efficient at promoting rooting than NAA. Indole-3-butyric acid is considered the most efficient auxin for root initiation and it is therefore the standard active ingredient in commercial rooting substances (Rambaran, 2013).

For the commercial application of IBA, three common delivery methods are utilized, which include the basal quick-dip, dilute soak and powder (Blythe et al., 2007).

2.7.6 Age of ramets

The maturation status of the mother plant or ramet can affect the rooting ability of cuttings (Stuepp et al., 2017) in that when coppices are harvested from too old ramets, then rooting response and survival is very low or can even fail since *Eucalyptus* exhibits both easy-to-root and difficult-to-root ages and species (recalcitrant to rooting) (Stuepp et al., 2017). According to (Maile & Nieuwenhuis, 1996) it was found out that cuttings taken from mature trees failed to root even with the application of exogenous auxin (Rambaran, 2013). It was however noted that that rooting in cuttings was only increased by in increasing the concentration of IBA taken from 15 year old trees and from mother garden whose ramets are more than 5 years old (Rasmussen et al., 2015). In contrast, cuttings taken from 5-year-old trees and ramets displayed higher survival and rooting percentages in the absence of IBA (Rose, 2015). This is because cuttings, being more juvenile may possess sufficient endogenous auxin required to initiate the rooting process (Stuepp et al., 2017)

2.7.7 Environmental factors

The rooting of cuttings may be significantly influenced by the application of auxin but their initial survival is directly dependent on the environmental conditions (Rambaran, 2013).

Light and temperature conditions to which the parent plants are exposed can influence the rooting in the harvested cuttings. It is however possible to manipulate these conditions to ensure maximum rooting of cuttings (Mokotedi et al., 2000), and therefore they should be maintained at optimal levels. These factors can influence the uptake and metabolism of nutrients and hormones, (Selvan, 2015).

Light, specifically affects the levels of carbohydrate in parent plants which should be sufficient not only to supply the cuttings with the energy required to initiate roots, but also to regulate rooting (Francisco De Assis et al., 2004). The temperature to which parent plants are subjected have the potential to affect the quality and quantity of cuttings produced, (Rambaran, 2013) as well as the associated root development.

Optimum light conditions, temperatures and relative humidity are all essential to promote survival and rooting of cuttings (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016). Since cuttings initially have no roots, they have no means of replacing transpired water, and it is therefore essential to maintain an atmosphere with a low evaporative demand to ensure that transpiration from the cuttings is minimized (Davies, n.d.).

According to (Rambaran, 2013) the propagation environment must be regulated at the temperature that stimulates metabolism at the base of the cutting and promotes adventitious root formation and temperatures exceeding the optimum may pose deleterious consequences such as increasing transpiration which subsequently creates tissue water deficits (Davies, n.d.) hence that's is why a greenhouse and tunnel domes should be made of white polythene paper to successfully root clonal cuttings (Africa, 2014).

Irradiance within the propagation environment must be sufficient to enable photosynthesis to occur as the formation of adventitious roots is a carbohydrate dependent process (Corrêa et al., 2005). The effect of season, with changing temperature and light intensity, photoperiod and humidity, can significantly affect the survival and rooting of cuttings (Mokotedi et al., 2000). It was recommended that to achieve maximum rooting the temperature of the rooting environment should be between 20°C – 30°C (Africa, 2014). Water loss is a major cause of cutting death prior to root formation, since for cell division to occur it is necessary that cells of the tissue be turgid.(Gem et al., 2006)

The humidity within the rooting environment needs to be high to reduce transpiration through the leaves (Nakhooda & Jain, 2016), however, excessively high humidity as well as wetness could be deleterious to cuttings by impairing gas exchange and facilitating the proliferation of diseases (SPGS, 2009). It was determined (Tamak, 2022) that for *E. grandis*, *E. urophylla* and *E. grandis* x *E. urophylla*, increase in light intensity and decreased relative humidity promoted the rooting of cuttings (Kindie & Abdala, 2021)

2.7.8 Rooting Media

Rooting media should be able to maintain ideal conditions of aeration and moisture retention (Dhiman & Gandhi, 2014a) as well as suitable pH (Gunaseena, Peris, K., , & De silva, C, 2007) so as to encourage fast and uniform root development in rooted cuttings.

In addition, the media needs to be light in weight, well drained, inert, inorganic matter and free from pest and weed seed (Dhiman & Gandhi, 2014a). Very coarse rooting media such as rice husks and grasses encourage callus formation at the base of cuttings with low rooting, whilst, too fine media lead to excessive moisture retention and rotting of cuttings (Dhiman & Gandhi, 2014a), thus a moderately textured rooting medium should be used. It was reported that increased rooting ability is correlated with the type of rooting media (Jeremiah et al., 2018) among other factors.

The root of plants must obtain sufficient water, oxygen and the nutrients from the surrounding environment within the rooting medium (Iasiah & Khanif, 2004) for their metabolic requirements. These metabolic processes of the root system excrete carbon dioxide and other gases which should be eliminated from the root environment within a certain time (Iasiah & Khanif, 2004). This can be effectively achieved when the growing medium structure is soft and porous enough (Iasiah & Khanif, 2004). It should however be strong enough to provide anchorage and support for the plantlets.

2.7.9 Time lapse between harvesting and insertion of cuttings into pots

Theoretically, keeping other factors constant, it is expected to have a higher survival percentage for cuttings inserted less than 60 minutes after harvesting, compared to those inserted after 120 minutes. This is so due to the turgidity loss effect as water-stressed cuttings are more prone to diseases and pests (Murugan, 2007), which should increase in cuttings inserted at 60 minutes, 120 and 180 minutes respectively.

This is because initially cuttings do not have roots and thus they cannot produce Abscisic acid to regulate their water stress responses and lack effective organs to replace lost water through

transpiration (Davies, 2005). Since coppices take up water poorly through the stem cutting base and any foliage immersed in the aqueous medium yet the main entry points of water is adventitious roots (Davies, 2005), water loss is expected to be higher than water up take in the harvested cuttings that stay longer before insertion; thereby affecting their subsequent development into plantlets.

Furthermore, cutting development into plantlets is expected to decrease with increasing time before cutting insertion as a result of collapse of phloem and xylem vessels due to decline in hydraulic conductivity of cuttings which also increases with increasing time after coppice harvesting (Davies, 2005).

CHAPTER THREE: MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Description of the study area.

This research was done at the National Tree Seed Center (NTSC) nursery in Namanve-Mukono District. It is situated at an elevation of 1155 metres above sea level, with geographical coordinates of 0°20'26.6"N, 32°41'39.0"E. This place experiences a mean annual rainfall of 1200 mm, a mean annual temperature ranging between 21–23°C and an average humidity of 80%; with a tropical savanna climate (Lumu et al., 2014).

NTSC was chosen because it is certified by Sawlog Production Grant Scheme (SPGS) to produce clonal Eucalyptus plantlets and it encourages seed/seedling production related research, equipped with most of the required materials and equipment for this cause. It also has good built-up facilities such as tree nurseries, clonal eucalyptus mother gardens, an equipped laboratory, ambient rooms and the cold room of 4°C, which are helpful in the process of raising quality seedlings/plantlets and seeds of over 100 indigenous and exotic species. It produces seedlings and seeds of common tree species such as *Pinus caribaea*, *Eucalyptus grandis*, *Maesopsis eminii*, *Terminalia superba*, *Araucaria cunninghamii*, etc; fruit trees like grafted mangoes, avocados, budded oranges, pawpaw, jackfruit, passion fruits, etc; as well as agro-forestry species, medicinal trees, and ornamental tree species.

3.2 Materials:

Three tree species of clonal Eucalyptus hybrids were considered under this experiment and these are; GC796, GC796/2, and GU7. The reason why these tree species were selected is first and foremost because they are among the widely grown species in Uganda (Nakabonge & Matovu, 2021) but also the fact that they are proved to have reasonable rooting abilities (Namujehe & Orikiriza, 2014), in addition to them being among those that are raised at this nursery site.

Other important materials that were used in this study include scissors, secateurs, rooting hormone, fungicide, buckets, water, watering cans, polyethene pots, white polyethene tunnels, lake sand, red soil, etc.

3.3 Research design

The design that was used in this experiment was a factorial treatment method in which the effects of three different time durations were investigated on the survival of the three clonal types. 450 cuttings of GC796, GC796/2, GU7 were sub categorized into three batches

according to time duration treatment, with each batch consisting of 50 cuttings per clonal type, per time duration treatment. This implies that under every time duration treatment were 150 cuttings, 50 per clonal type. These were subjected to three different time duration treatments, that is, 60, 120 and 180 minutes respectively before insertion of the cuttings into the pots.

3.4 Experimental setup:

All the pots were placed in the same tunnel under a greenhouse shade so that they are exposed to uniform environmental and experimental conditions. This was done to eliminate variation that could be brought about by unintended differences in treatments like amount of irrigation water, concentration of fungicides or environmental conditions such as relative humidity in the growing chamber.

3.5 Soil mixing and pot filling:

Red soil together with lake sand were thoroughly mixed in the ratio of 5:1 respectively so as to get an appropriate soil mixture which was later used for potting. The red soil was to increase water retention as well as improving the soil structure whilst sand was to improve porosity since rooting media need to maintain an ideal combination of aeration and moisture retention to encourage fast and uniform rooting (Dhiman & Gandhi, 2014).

The soil mixture was then filled in black polyethene pots of approximately 6cm long and then placed in the tunnel base that is lined with flexible ‘wires’ at a distance of about 0.8 m from each other, bent across the length of the tunnel base to make a ‘semi-circle-like structure’ upon which the transparent polythene layer was later on laid to come up with a complete tunnel, within which the plantlets were raised (Selvan, 2015).

The pots for all the samples were placed in the same tunnel so as to ensure that all the growth conditions for all samples are relatively the same and to remove bias as a result of different micro-environment conditions that may be present in different tunnels, such as moisture levels, fertilization levels, fungicide treatment levels, etc

3.6 Coppice harvesting:

The cuttings for all the clonal types were selected from the three-year old mother garden, which is separated into different compartments by trenches, according to species. The first batch of 150 cuttings comprising 50 cuttings per clonal type was harvested using secateurs, processed and inserted at 60 minutes after processing. This was accomplished by a group of 3 people with each person handling a single clonal type. An average of 3 vertically oriented coppices were

harvested from a given ramet and placed in a bucket of fresh water, from where they were carried to the preparation site, in order to minimize the cases of coppice desiccation that would result in a reduction in rooting after cutting insertion (Santana et al, 2010). The second and third batches were also harvested following the same procedure, which were prepared and inserted at 120 and 180 minutes respectively after processing.

3.7 Clipping and fungicide application:

At the preparation site, the coppices were processed into cuttings of approximately 8cm long (D. Naidu & Jones, 2015) using scissors and soaked in a ridomil gold fungicide solution (Do et al., 2020). This was to keep the cuttings turgid before insertion was done as well as protecting them from fungal infection (Balasundaran et al., 2000), that would affect their effective subsequent development into plantlets. The cuttings were left with two alternate half leaves to enhance some level of photosynthesis as well as reducing transpirational water loss by their reduced surface area (Jeremiah et al., 2018).

Before cutting insertion was done, the pots were irrigated using watering cans, with water containing the fungicide in order to sterilize the rooting medium. After cutting insertion into the pots, a thin film of aqueous solution of the ridomil fungicide was again applied to the inserted cuttings using a small hand pressure pump, so as to further provide control of certain diseases caused by members of the Oomycete class of fungi (Selvan, 2015).

3.8 Preparation of the growing tunnel:

There are already constructed tunnel bases of about 0.8m wide at the NTSC nursery site under a greenhouse shade, whose sides are made up roughly cemented walls that are about 20cm from the ground level, to prevent outflow of irrigated water sideways. One of these tunnels was prepared by first filling three quarters of the tunnel base with sand in order to make a levelled ground on which the pots were later placed. Porous polythene layer was then laid on the levelled tunnel base before the pots were placed, so as to allow optimum water infiltration especially while watering the pots, since too much water could be a source of mortality due to damping off (Glocke et al., 2006).

Before the transparent polyethene was added to make a complete tunnel, flexible ‘wires’ were fixed from one side of the tunnel base, bent across to the side of it, to make a semi-circle-like structure, erected above its whole length, with a distance of about 0.8 m between one ‘wire’ and the other. It is onto this structure that two transparent polyethene sheets were laid after cutting insertion and irrigation was completed, to cover up the cuttings under the air tight

environment. This minimizes the rate of transpiration by cuttings (Kamis et al, 2016) since the transpired water is captured within the tunnel and returns back to the cutting on condensation. The transparent polyethylene allows the regulated entry of light to enhance the required level of physiological processes for the cuttings to develop into cuttings.

After placing the polyethylene layer over the tunnel, it was fixed by surrounding it with bricks and sand in order to have a firmly fixed tunnel.

3.9 Rooting hormone application and cutting insertion:

The clipped cutting basal ends were dipped into a powder of 0.6 ppm of rootex rooting hormone before being inserted in the rooting media, to encourage root growth and development at the base of the cuttings. This hormone contains indole3-butyric acid (IBA) as its active ingredient and it was applied with a fine layer to about 0.5cm from the base of the cuttings (Bryant & Trueman, 2015) and inserted to about 1.5cm (Dhiman & Gandhi, 2014b) deep into the pots. This hormone was used not only because it is the one that was being used at the NTSC nursery where the research was carried out, but also because it is considered as the best artificial hormone used for rooting of cuttings (Khajehpour et al., 2014).

The pots were watered with ridomil treated water followed by an aqueous solution of 'Easy Gro' water soluble fertilizer as an immediate source of nutrients for the cuttings, just before the cuttings were inserted into the pots. Cuttings were then inserted into the moist pots to about 1.5cm deep, after which a thin layer of ridomil fungicide was applied to the inserted cuttings using a hand pressure pump, so as to reduce chances of pathogen attack (Selvan, 2015).

3.10 Irrigation and disease control:

As the experiment was running, the tunnel was opened at a weekly basis and the 'potted' cuttings irrigated with a controlled amount of fungicide treated water to ensure control of disease causing pathogens that could have developed within the tunnel as well as supplying cuttings with the required moisture for their effective root development. This was always done in the morning to reduce chances of transpiration.

3.11 Sampling procedure:

A simple random sampling was used in the ramet selection during coppice harvesting, whereby there was no specific criterion followed, so as to eliminate bias. Choice of the coppices to harvest from a given ramet followed a purposive sampling criterion, so that only semi-mature terminal coppice 'stems' were selected, since they are the ones recommended for better nursery

performance. These were considered since very young coppices can easily suffer from water stress and die out, whereas old ones experience low rooting abilities (Rambaran, 2013).

3.12 Data collection:

At the end of the four -week time period, the tunnel was opened and cuttings were then assessed for general survival, root development as well as leaf development. The general survival was assessed by counting the number of live plantlets for all the experimental samples and the data recorded appropriately in a table as shown in appendix 1. The plantlets were considered live only when they had developed leaves.

The data on root development was assessed by uprooting the plantlets one by one, counting and recording the number of roots that had developed, as well as measuring using a ruler, and recording the length of the longest root that had developed on every plantlet. This was done by handling a single treatment sample at a time and the raw data is shown in appendices; 11, 111 and 1V, for GC796, GC796/2 and GU7 respectively.

Assessing data on leaf development also followed the same procedure whereby the number of leaves for every plantlet was counted and recorded as well as measuring using a ruler the length of the longest leaf and recording it in the table as shown in appendices; V, V1, V11, for GC796, GC796/2 and GU7 respectively.

This was done for all the cuttings that had developed into plantlets, handling each experimental unit at a time.

3.13 Data analysis:

The raw data was entered in Microsoft excel first from where it was organized and later transferred to SPSS for further analysis. In SPSS, the findings were analyzed using One-Way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance), by comparing means of different treatment categories, to determine if there was a significant difference in the effect of different time duration treatments on cutting survival in terms of number of live plantlets, root and leaf development, under every experimental treatment.

However, for both GU7 and GC796/2 the lowest survival percentage was experienced for the cuttings which were inserted after 180 minutes unlike GC796 which attained the lowest survival percentage for cuttings which were inserted after 60 minutes.

4.2 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on root development of GC796 cuttings.

According to results presented in table 1, plantlets inserted at 60 minutes had the highest number of roots. It is further observed that the number of roots per plantlet reduced with increasing time of planting after coppice harvesting. However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the number of roots among plantlets planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F= 2.911$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

Table 1: Mean “number of roots” and “length of the longest root” of GC796 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
No. of roots	60	15	7.00	3.464	.894
	120	24	5.88	2.365	.483
	180	22	4.77	2.671	.570
	Total	61	5.75	2.862	.366
Length of the longest root	60	15	9.0467	3.47889	.89825
	120	24	13.7750	4.61974	.94300
	180	22	11.7000	5.27103	1.12379
	Total	61	11.8639	4.91776	.62965

Table 2: Analysis of variance for mean differences in the “number of roots” and “length of the longest root” of GC796 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting.

		DF	F	P- value
No. of roots	Between Groups	2	2.911	.062
	Within Groups	58		

Total	60		
Length of the longest root	Between Groups	2	4.833 .011
	Within Groups	58	
Total	60		

With regard to the length of the longest root, the results show that mean longest root was recorded among plantlets inserted 120 minutes after coppice harvesting (Table 1). ANOVA showed that there was a significant difference in mean longest root among plantlets inserted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=4.833$; $DF=2$; $P=0.011$).

A post hoc test further revealed that between 60 minutes and 180 minutes, as well as 60 minutes and 120 minutes exist a significant difference in “number of roots” and “lengths of the longest root” respectively (Table 3)

Table 3: Multiple comparisons of mean longest root length among plantlets of GC796 planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting.

Dependent Variable	(I) Time	(J) Time	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P-Value
No. of roots	60	120	1.125	.913	.223
		180	2.227*	.929	.020
	120	60	-1.125	.913	.223
		180	1.102	.819	.184
	180	60	-2.227*	.929	.020
		120	-1.102	.819	.184
Length of the longest root	60	120	-4.7283*	1.5242	.003
		180	-2.6533	1.5506	.092
	120	60	4.7283*	1.5242	.003
		180	2.0750	1.3668	.134
	180	60	2.6533	1.5506	.092
		120	-2.0750	1.3668	.134

4.3 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on leaf development of GC796 cuttings.

According to results presented in table 4, plantlets inserted at 120 minutes had the highest number of leaves. However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the number of leaves among plantlets planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F= 1.185$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

Table 4: Mean “number of leaves” and “length of the longest leaf” of GC796 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
No. of leaves	60	15	8.8000	4.84326	1.25052
	120	24	11.5417	6.28303	1.28252
	180	22	10.1364	4.90185	1.04508
	Total	61	10.3607	5.49555	.70363
Length of the longest leaf	60	15	3.1733	1.29696	.33487
	120	24	2.9292	1.23798	.25270
	180	22	3.0909	1.49122	.31793
	Total	61	3.0475	1.32986	.17027

Table 5: Analysis of variance for mean differences in the “number of leaves” and “length of the longest leaf” of GC796 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting.

		DF	F	P- value
No. of leaves	Between Groups	2	1.185	.313
	Within Groups	58		
	Total	60		

Length of the longest leaf	Between Groups	2	.169	.845
	Within Groups	58		
	Total	60		

With regard to the length of the longest leaf, the results show that mean longest leaf was recorded among plantlets inserted 60 minutes after coppice harvesting (Table 4). However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in mean longest leaf among plantlets inserted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=0.169$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

4.4 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on root development of GC796/2 cuttings planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

According to results presented in table 6, plantlets inserted at 60 minutes had the highest number of roots. However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the number of roots among plantlets planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=1.533$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

Table 6: Mean “number of roots” and “length of the longest root” of GC796/2 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
No. of roots	60	26	7.23	4.926	.966
	120	27	5.41	3.935	.757
	180	23	7.04	3.364	.701
	Total	76	6.53	4.181	.480
Length of the longest root	60	26	10.1308	4.48596	.87977
	120	27	11.5296	7.20079	1.38579
	180	23	9.4130	3.60647	.75200
	Total	76	10.4105	5.41124	.62071

Table 7: Analysis of variance for mean differences in the “number of roots” and “length of the longest root” of GC796/2 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting.

		DF	F	P-Value
No. of roots	Between Groups	2	1.533	.223
	Within Groups	73		
	Total	75		
Length of the longest root	Between Groups	2	1.003	.372
	Within Groups	73		
	Total	75		

With regard to the length of the longest root, the results show that mean longest root was recorded among plantlets inserted 120 minutes after coppice harvesting (Table 6). However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in mean longest root among plantlets inserted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=1.003$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

4.5 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on leaf development of GC796/2 cuttings planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

According to results presented in table 8, plantlets inserted at 180 minutes had the highest number of leaves. However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the number of leaves among plantlets planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F= 0.910$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

Table 8: Mean “number of leaves” and “length of the longest leaf” of GC796/2 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
No. of leaves	60	26	10.3846	3.98072	.78068
	120	27	9.6667	4.77171	.91832
	180	23	11.3043	3.98217	.83034

	Total	76	10.4079	4.27451	.49032
Length of the longest leaf	60	26	3.0962	1.12160	.21996
	120	27	2.5037	1.38049	.26568
	180	23	3.1565	1.60675	.33503
	Total	76	2.9039	1.38828	.15925

Table 8: Analysis of variance for mean differences in the “number of leaves” and “length of the longest leaf” of GC796/2 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting.

		DF	F	P-Value
No. of leaves	Between Groups	2	.910	.407
	Within Groups	73		
	Total	75		
Length of the longest leaf	Between Groups	2	1.789	.174
	Within Groups	73		
	Total	75		

With regard to the length of the longest leaf, the results show that mean longest leaf was recorded among plantlets inserted 180 minutes after coppice harvesting (Table 8). However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in mean longest root among plantlets inserted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=1.789$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

4.6 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on root development of GU7 cuttings planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

According to results presented in table 10, plantlets inserted at 180 minutes had the highest number of roots. However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the number of roots among plantlets planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=0.80$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

Table 10: Mean “number of roots” and “length of the longest root” of GU7 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
No. of roots	60	13	6.31	4.250	1.179
	120	11	5.73	4.692	1.415
	180	3	6.67	3.215	1.856
	Total	27	6.11	4.209	.810
Length of the longest root	60	13	13.7231	6.44815	1.78839
	120	11	12.6727	5.77115	1.74007
	180	3	10.2667	3.93107	2.26961
	Total	27	12.9111	5.86084	1.12792

Table 11: Analysis of variance for mean differences in the “number of roots” and “length of the longest root” of GU7 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting.

		DF	F	P-Value
No. of roots	Between Groups	2	.080	.923
	Within Groups	24		
	Total	26		
Length of the longest root	Between Groups	2	.420	.662
	Within Groups	24		
	Total	26		

With regard to the length of the longest root, the results show that mean longest root was recorded among plantlets inserted 60 minutes after coppice harvesting (Table 10). ANOVA

showed that there was no significant difference in mean longest root among plantlets inserted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=0.420$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$). It is further observed that mean root length per plantlet reduced with increasing time of planting after coppice harvesting.

4.7 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on leaf development of GU7 cuttings planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

According to results presented in table 12, plantlets inserted at 180 minutes had the highest number of leaves. It is further observed that the number of leaves per plantlet reduced with increasing time of planting after coppice harvesting. However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the number of roots among plantlets planted at 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=0.158$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

Table 9: Mean “number of leaves” and “length of the longest leaf” of GU7 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
No. of leaves	60	13	13.4615	7.96467	2.20900
	120	11	13.3636	6.50035	1.95993
	180	3	11.0000	1.00000	.57735
	Total	27	13.1481	6.79764	1.30821
Length of the longest leaf	60	13	2.1462	1.24874	.34634
	120	11	2.8818	1.34894	.40672
	180	3	2.0667	1.12398	.64893
	Total	27	2.4370	1.28786	.24785

Table 10: Analysis of variance for mean differences in the “number of leaves” and “length of the longest leaf” of GU7 cuttings planted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting.

		DF	F	P- Value
No. of leaves	Between Groups	2	.158	.855
	Within Groups	24		
	Total	26		
Length of the longest leaf	Between Groups	2	1.122	.342
	Within Groups	24		
	Total	26		

With regard to the length of the longest leaf, the results show that mean longest leaf was recorded among plantlets inserted 120 minutes after coppice harvesting (Table 12). However, ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in mean longest root among plantlets inserted 60, 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting ($F=1.122$; $DF=2$; $P>0.05$).

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

5.1 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on survival of cuttings.

It was assumed that, the survival percentage should decrease with increasing time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion due to the effect of decreasing turgidity of cuttings which guarantee decreased rooting. However, this wasn't the case for the two clonal types, i.e. GC796 and GC796/2. This could have been due to the fact that the cuttings were kept in water during the time before which they were inserted.

Survival percentage of GU7 however, decreased with increasing time after cutting insertion. This could be due to the effect of turgidity loss, as a result of collapse of phloem and xylem vessels (Davies, 2005), since water-stressed cuttings are more prone to diseases and pests (Murugan, 2007). As well, it could be because cuttings do not have roots and thus they cannot produce Abscisic acid to regulate their water stress responses and lack effective organs to replace lost water through transpiration (Davies, 2005), which would be important for cutting survival. Since coppices take up water poorly through the stem cutting base and any foliage immersed in the aqueous medium yet the main entry points of water is adventitious roots (Davies, 2005), water loss is expected to be higher than water up take in the harvested cuttings that stay longer before insertion; thereby affecting their subsequent development into plantlets.

The survival percentages for GU7 consistently decreased with increasing time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion. This could be attributed to a combination of factors which could be genetic differences as well as experimental factors (Sciences, n.d.) like pH of the rooting medium, temperature (Kocyigit, 2015), as well as the effect of the position on the ramet from where the cuttings were taken (Murugan, 2007) whereby terminal cuttings are likely to survive more than the non-terminal cuttings, nevertheless this wasn't the case with (Nor Aini et al., 2010).

GC796/2 showed the highest survival percentage whereas GU7 showed the lowest survival percentage, which could imply that GCs exhibit higher survival rates than GUs. This could be attributed to the fact that GU varieties are more difficult to root than GC varieties (Linda, 2021), which may be due to chronological, morphological and physiological differences that might have existed among cuttings of different tree clonal types (Rambaran, 2013), for instance the age of the mother tree whereby the decline in rooting ability in woody tree species may be

linked to the effects of maturation, i.e. cuttings collected from younger ramets normally have greater vigor and ease to root (Stuepp et al., 2017).

5.2 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on root development.

GC796 plantlets inserted at 60 minutes had the highest number of roots which reduced with increasing time of planting after coppice harvesting. This could be attributed to the increasing water stress in cuttings with increasing time. This condition of water stress reduces the effectiveness of the cuttings physiological processes thereby leading to reduced root development.

GC796/2 plantlets inserted at 60 minutes had the highest number of roots. This could be due to the effect of appropriate turgor pressure which is expected to be most in the cuttings planted 60 minutes after coppice harvesting as compared to those planted 120 and 180 minutes after coppice harvesting, provided other factors are kept constant. This is turgor pressure is essential for enhancing the cutting physiological processes during root development (Murugan, 2007).

GU7 plantlets inserted 180 minutes after coppice harvesting had the highest number of roots. This is in contrary to the expected result of having the highest number of roots for cuttings planted 60 minutes after coppice harvesting. This could have been due to experimental and/or genetic factors that could have existed among the different batches of cuttings such as interaction of aeration and water- holding capacity of the rooting medium, whereby a well balanced oxygen and water-holding capacity promotes oxygen availability, transpiration, nutrient uptake, growth and aeration during root initiation (Mabizela et al., 2017).

Mean longest root for GU7 was recorded among plantlets inserted 60 minutes after coppice harvesting, and mean root length per plantlet of GU7 reduced with increasing time of planting after coppice harvesting. This could be attributed to the fact that increasing time before cutting insertion would result in the collapse of phloem and xylem vessels due to decline in hydraulic conductivity of cuttings which affects subsequent root development (Davies, 2005).

5.3 Effect of time lapse between coppice harvesting and cutting insertion on leaf development

GC796 plantlets inserted at 120 minutes had the highest number of leaves and mean longest leaf for GC796 was recorded among plantlets inserted 60 minutes after coppice harvesting.

This could have been due to a negative effect of red soil on leaf development (Jeremiah et al., 2018), which effect may vary among different clonal types. Also, efficiency of cutting propagation may be subject to the physiological conditions of the stock plants as well as time and place of cutting collection, according to Mitchell et al., (2004), and Crawford et al., (2016) respectively, which in turn may have an implication on leaf development.

GC796/2 plantlets inserted 180 minutes after coppice harvesting had the highest number of leaves and the mean longest leaf was recorded among plantlets inserted 180 minutes after coppice harvesting. This could be attributed to the fact that cutting propagation success may be correlated with auxin uptake regardless of other factors (Blythe et al., 2007) such as time of insertion. Therefore, the ability of the cutting with which it takes up the auxin affects its rooting potential which in turn has an implication on the cutting leaf development.

GU7 plantlets inserted at 180 minutes had the highest number of leaves. This could be attributed to other factors other than time lapse before cutting insertion such as fungal/disease attack. Furthermore, the fact that the effect on leaf development would more likely be significant in the field(Figueiredo et al., 2019) could have been the cause of such a finding.

Number of leaves per plantlet of GU7 reduced with increasing time of planting after coppice harvesting, however, mean longest leaf for GU7 was recorded among plantlets inserted 120 minutes after coppice harvesting. This could be because cuttings do not have roots and thus they cannot produce Abscisic acid to regulate their water stress responses which increase with increasing time after coppice harvesting, and lack effective organs to replace lost water through transpiration (Davies, 2005), which would be important for cutting survival. Since coppices take up water poorly through the stem cutting base and any foliage immersed in the aqueous medium yet the main entry points of water is adventitious roots (Davies, 2005), water loss is expected to be higher than water up take in the harvested cuttings that stay longer before insertion; thereby affecting their subsequent development into plantlets.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusions

- Generally, GC796/2 had the highest survival percentages, whereas GU7 had the least survival percentage under all the three different time lapse treatments. This was due to the fact that GUs have lower survival percentages than GCs.
- The survival percentage of GU7 reduced with increasing time lapse between coppice harvesting and planting. This was attributed to increased loss of turgidity.
- Unlike GU7, GC796 and GC796/2 cuttings had the highest survival percentage with cuttings planted 120 minutes after coppice harvesting. However, GC796 had the lowest survival percentage for cuttings planted 60 minutes after coppice harvesting unlike GC796/2 which attained the lowest survival percentage with cuttings inserted at 180 minutes. This was attributed to the difference in the genetic/experimental conditions.
- There was a significant difference in the number of roots and length of the longest root only with GC796 for cuttings planted 60 and 180 minutes; and 60 and 120 minutes respectively, after coppice harvesting. This was attributed to the fact that the effect of leaf development would be more realized after planting in the field.

6.2 Recommendations

6.2.1 Management

- According to the survival data collected, GC796 and GC796/2 should be inserted at 120 minutes since it is when the highest survival percentage was experienced, whereas GU7 should be inserted immediately after cutting preparation since the survival percentage consistently decreased with increasing time duration.

6.2.2 Research

- Additional research should be done while strictly controlling for all other factors, as well as using a larger sample size since it is most likely that such factors could have affected the findings of this study.

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APPENDICES:

Appendix 1: Number and percentage of cuttings that survived for all species under different time duration treatments of 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

Species	Time (mins)	No. Alive	No. Planted	Survival %
GC796	60	15	50	30
	120	24	50	48
	180	22	50	44
GC796/2	60	26	50	52
	120	27	50	54
	180	23	50	46
GU7	60	13	50	23
	120	11	50	22
	180	3	50	6

Appendix 11: Raw data on root development of GC796 plantlets for 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

60 mins			120 mins			180 mins		
Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)
1	3	9.2	1	3	27.2	1	5	9.1
2	7	8.9	2	4	12.3	2	3	7.5
3	5	15.4	3	8	7.3	3	6	9.4
4	8	3.9	4	5	7.9	4	3	8.5
5	5	10.2	5	4	8.4	5	3	6
6	5	11.3	6	12	10.7	6	2	9
7	12	8.8	7	5	17.3	7	11	10.1
8	12	7	8	7	12.2	8	3	12.5
9	9	9.5	9	8	12.6	9	3	9.9
10	3	9.4	10	5	15.3	10	3	22.1
11	4	5.1	11	5	23.9	11	6	13.1

12	2	15.5	12	4	14.2	12	6	8.5
13	12	3.2	13	11	13.3	13	4	22.4
14	8	9.4	14	9	10.5	14	6	10.8
15	10	8.9	15	5	14.7	15	8	17.7
			16	5	10.8	16	11	7.8
			17	4	15.1	17	4	16.5
			18	6	10	18	2	9.2
			19	5	15.9	19	2	21.4
			20	4	10.1	20	5	2.5
			21	6	15.9	21	7	12.8
			22	5	12.6	22	2	10.6
			23	8	16.1			
			24	3	16.3			

Appendix 111: Raw data on root development of GC796/2 plantlets for 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

60 mins			120 mins			180 mins		
Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)
1	4	8.1	1	0	0	1	4	8.9
2	4	6.6	2	0	0	2	6	8.8
3	11	8.4	3	7	12.8	3	10	6.1
4	3	7.9	4	5	19	4	4	13.3
5	2	11.2	5	20	15	5	13	8.9
6	10	7.9	6	2	22.6	6	7	5.3
7	4	10.6	7	7	12.9	7	5	10.7
8	5	13.2	8	1	2.6	8	6	8.1
9	7	11.8	9	8	15.9	9	7	7.6
10	27	7.5	10	8	28.8	10	12	12.1
11	10	15.2	11	7	11.2	11	16	3.9
12	8	8.7	12	2	20.1	12	7	5.9
13	3	6.5	13	1	18.2	13	6	16.2
14	7	3.3	14	6	15.2	14	8	5.9

15	11	9.7	15	3	3.7	15	8	15.2
16	5	12.3	16	7	9.3	16	3	15
17	11	11.3	17	9	2.9	17	10	7.5
18	5	16.2	18	6	4.6	18	7	9.8
19	7	20.2	19	5	17.1	19	1	11.5
20	6	11.5	20	9	12.5	20	6	11.8
21	8	8.1	21	7	14.7	21	5	6.8
22	11	5.9	22	4	11.8	22	5	13.1
23	3	22.1	23	4	5.9	23	6	4.1
24	4	9.2	24	6	3.6			
25	6	4.6	25	4	14.3			
26	6	5.4	26	4	10			
			27	4	6.6			

Appendix 1V: Raw data on root development of GU7 plantlets for 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

60 mins			120 mins			180 mins		
Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of roots	Length of the longest root(cm)
1	3	16.7	1	4	25.5	1	8	13.2
2	15	6.3	2	1	18.4	2	3	5.8
3	5	19.1	3	7	13.2	3	9	11.8
4	2	8	4	5	7.6			
5	5	22.6	5	1	9.5			
6	1	6.1	6	2	7.1			
7	1	23.1	7	10	8.8			
8	8	17.8	8	13	18.2			
9	9	18.2	9	14	8.2			
10	5	3.6	10	2	11.3			
11	7	13.4	11	4	11.6			
12	9	10.9						
13	12	12.6						

Appendix V: Raw data on leaf development of GC796 plantlets for 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

60 mins			120 mins			180 mins		
Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)
1	8	4.5	1	12	0.9	1	2	0.2
2	8	5.7	2	12	2.7	2	8	4.1
3	11	3.1	3	6	1.6	3	8	3.6
4	5	2.9	4	6	1.4	4	10	1.5
5	2	2.5	5	6	0.6	5	9	2.5
6	11	4.2	6	8	4.4	6	18	2.6
7	6	3.2	7	14	2.2	7	22	2.9
8	24	2.9	8	14	3.8	8	12	1.6
9	9	1.6	9	26	3.1	9	10	2.6
10	6	2.6	10	8	3.1	10	16	4
11	7	1.1	11	10	1.5	11	20	3.4
12	8	3.6	12	4	2.6	12	7	5
13	7	1.2	13	14	2.6	13	8	6
14	10	3.9	14	12	6	14	13	3.9
15	10	4.6	15	32	2.8	15	8	4.4
			16	8	2.3	16	8	2.8
			17	16	3	17	7	4.1
			18	8	2.9	18	6	1.5
			19	14	3.9	19	10	4.7
			20	8	3	20	8	1.4
			21	8	4.6	21	7	4.4
			22	12	3.7	22	6	0.8
			23	9	3.6			
			24	10	4			

Appendix V1: Raw data for leaf development of GC796/2 cuttings for 60, 120 and 180 minutes

60 mins			120 mins			180 mins		
Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)
1	9	1.5	1	2	0.4	1	8	0.3
2	7	3.8	2	3	0.4	2	15	3.5
3	10	4.6	3	8	3.1	3	18	2.8
4	8	0.6	4	4	0.3	4	10	1.2
5	7	2.5	5	10	5.1	5	10	4.5
6	10	4.3	6	2	0.3	6	16	2.2
7	10	2.4	7	12	1.5	7	10	1.4
8	8	2.5	8	5	2.4	8	10	4.6
9	15	5.2	9	14	3.6	9	10	5.9
10	18	4.4	10	11	3.8	10	18	4.8
11	7	4.6	11	14	1.9	11	20	3.2
12	8	2.4	12	14	3.9	12	10	1.9
13	5	2.1	13	8	1.4	13	9	5.5
14	16	2.7	14	20	4.8	14	10	4.6
15	20	2.8	15	12	1.4	15	16	1.7
16	15	3.3	16	13	2.9	16	7	3.3
17	6	1.4	17	7	2	17	8	4.3
18	6	2.8	18	13	3.4	18	10	5.2
19	6	3.9	19	14	2.6	19	11	1.5
20	8	4.4	20	10	4	20	10	4.2
21	13	3.3	21	14	4	21	12	1.5
22	12	3.9	22	12	2.6	22	4	1.4
23	10	2.6	23	16	2.1	23	8	3.1
24	10	2.5	24	8	2.6			
25	14	2.5	25	8	3.9			
26	12	3.5	26	3	1.1			
			27	4	2.1			

Appendix V11: Raw data for leaf development of GU7 cuttings for 60, 120 and 180 minutes

60 mins			120 mins			180 mins		
Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)	Plantlet no.	No of leaves	Length of the longest root(cm)
1	5	3.1	1	11	3.6	1	10	3.3
2	12	4.6	2	13	2.3	2	11	1.1
3	8	0.6	3	14	2.1	3	12	1.8
4	10	2.7	4	12	3.8	4		
5	17	2.2	5	8	4.5	5		
6	2	0.3	6	4	1.7	6		
7	8	0.5	7	15	2.5	7		
8	20	2.6	8	26	5.2	8		
9	12	1.6	9	10	2.5	9		
10	27	1.4	10	10	0.4	10		
11	13	2.1	11	24	3.1	11		
12	29	2.9	12			12		
13	12	3.3	13			13		